

kilograms of loamy soil mixed with 200 g single superphosphate was spread on a 15- × 7.5- × 22.5-cm galvanized iron tray flooded to 7.5 cm, and 250 g mother culture broadcast. A thick mat of BGA formed in about 10 d.

The water was allowed to evaporate and the dry BGA flakes with some soil were collected and ground for inoculum.

Inoculated plots produced a luxuriant growth of BGA, about 4 kg fresh weight/m². No microscopic observations were made because of the lack of facilities. The dominant algae biomass resembled *Anabaena* morphologically. A BGA bloom during maximum tillering continued up to panicle initiation, then gradually diminished.

Effect of inoculating BGA with and without applied N on irrigated rice yields. Himachal Pradesh, India, 1990 wet season.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm) at harvest	Panicle length (cm) at harvest	Grain number (no./panicle) at harvest
BGA ₀ N ₀	2.1	5.2	80.0	18.3	131
BGA ₀ N ₃₀	2.4	6.4	80.5	19.4	147
BGA ₀ N ₆₀	2.6	7.7	82.9	20.0	150
BGA ₀ N ₉₀	2.9	8.6	84.0	20.0	151
BGA ₁₀ N ₀	2.5	6.2	81.0	20.4	159
BGA ₁₀ N ₃₀	3.0	6.6	81.0	19.5	168
BGA ₁₀ N ₆₀	3.1	8.1	81.5	21.0	174
BGA ₁₀ N ₉₀	3.5	9.0	82.5	21.3	177
LSD (0.05)					
BGA	0.4				
N	0.1	0.4			
BGA×N	0.2	0.6			

Grain and straw yields were highest with 10 kg BGA + 90 kg N/ha (see table). Grain yields, but not straw yields, were

influenced significantly by BGA. Nearly half a ton extra grain was obtained from BGA application. □

Integrated fertilizer management

Long-range effect of continuous cropping and fertilizer application on yield stability of Wet Season (ws) rice

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We began a long-range fertilizer experiment in 1977 (Apr-Sep) WS. Treatments included three N levels, three P levels, and two K levels, with a no-treatment control.

The experimental area was double-cropped wetland with sandy clay loam soil (riverine alluvium deposited over laterite soil), 71% sand, and 5% silt.

Initial soil analysis on composite samples from the top 20 cm layer showed pH 5.2; EC 0.25 dS/m; 0.72% organic C; and 156, 31, 178 kg available N, P, K/ha. The experimental layout was a partially confounded randomized block design with four replications. Jaya was the test variety.

Grain yields averaged over 14 WSs in continuous WS cropping experiment. Kerala, India, 1977-91.

Fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	No P	17.6 kg P/ha	35 kg P/ha	NoK	33 kg K/ha	Mean(N)
40 kg N/ha	3.4	3.9	3.9	3.8	3.7	3.8
80 kg N/ha	3.8	4.2	4.3	4.2	4.0	4.1
120 kg N/ha	3.9	4.4	4.5	4.2	4.3	4.3
Mean (P & K)	3.7	4.2	4.2	4.1	4.0	
No K	3.8	4.2	4.3			
33 kg K/ha	3.7	4.1	4.2			
LSD N and P	0.2					

N level significantly affected yields for 9 yr (see table). P level significantly affected yields for the last 10 yr. The delayed response to P may be due to a residual effect. No response to potash occurred, perhaps because of the high soil K content. With no fertilizer, yields varied from 3.7 t/ha in 1977 to 2.7 t/ha in 1990. □

Crop management

Effect of tillage practices on deepwater rice (DWR) yield and return

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In DWR areas, land preparation is done when water recedes. We studied the effect of six different tillage practices in a randomized block design with four replications in 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Apr-Dec).

Soil at the experimental site was clay loam (Aridisol) with pH 8.2, 0.52% organic C, 11 kg available P, 248 kg K/ha.

Rice variety Jalmagna was direct seeded in rows 25 cm apart on 20 Apr

1988 and 25 Apr 1989. Plot size was 90 m². Basal fertilizer was 40 kg N, 8.8 kg P/ha. Water started to rise in Jul, reaching a maximum 240 cm in Aug 1988 and 210 cm in Sep 1989.

Yields differed significantly both years (see table). Highest grain yield, net return, and benefit:cost ratio were with one moldboard plowing plus two plowings by country plow, with planking after each plowing. □